

Project management and industry 4.0: a scientific bibliometric study.

Luis Fernando Moreira
Cassiano Duarte
Valter Marcos Monteiro Fortes
Adrieli Alves Pereira Radaelli
Debora Machado da Silva
Ebersom Cordeiro de Almeida

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SUMMARY

Project management is a set of management tools that helps the company to avoid surprises during the execution of projects allied to the concept of industry 4.0 or the fourth industrial revolution, which has been accompanying the increase in the development of new technologies and aims to stimulate industrial growth. Thus, this study was conceived based on Lotka's Law (scientific productivity of authors), Bradford's Law (journal productivity), and Zipf's Law (frequency of words), and to identify the main areas and countries of knowledge that research on the subject from 2010 to March 20 20. The research was developed through a study and in the *Scopus* database having as analysis criteria the most cited works, the main authors (relevant), and the main keywords. Thus, it was identified to be rudimentary as well as insufficient publications in the period from 2010 to 20 20 with a total of 63 documents on the research topic with a peak of publications in 2019. Germany is the cradle of industry 4.0 had the largest number of published documents, Brazil has researchers and articles with a good number of citations and impact factors in the publications analyzed.

Keywords: Management of projects. Industry 4.0. Bibliometric study.

1 INTRODUCTION

Due to globalization, according to Cavalieri (2005), the changes in the world scenario, which is increasingly competing, generate the obligation of faster results, with higher quality and lower costs. In this sense, Casarotto (2002) states that project management becomes a very useful and valuable instrument for the organization, improving products and the manufacturing process, making them more agile and amortizing costs.

Industry 4.0 is a new concept, recently indicated, and I was born in Germany that brings together the development, inclusion, and use of technological innovations in the circuses of automation, control, and information technology, superimposed on integrated manufacturing processes (KAGERMANN; WAHLSTER; HELBIG, 2013). Thus it is plausible to encompass the importance of research on the terms project management allied to industry 4.0 which are peculiar phenomena of recent years, have awakened the contemporary merit and growing demand of researchers in various parts of the world for the subject (DAUDT; WILLCOX, 2016).

Thus, the present work addressed the application of a bibliometric (GUEDES, BORSCHIVER, 2005), addressing the terms project management (PMI, 2019), combined with

industry 4.0 (KAGERMANN; WAHLSTER; HELBIG, 2013) Given the relevance of these terms, the **objective of this article was to analyze the evolution of scientific production regarding the themes project management and industry 4.0 based on Lotka's Law (scientific productivity of authors), Bradford's Law (journal productivity) and Zipf's Law (frequency of words), and to identify the country which published the most from 2010 to March 20 20. (LOTKA, 1926; BRADFORD, 1934; ZIPF, 1949).**

2 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 CONCEPT OF PROJECT MANAGEMENT AND ITS BENEFITS.

Academic studies on project management have attracted exclusive attention when related to how projects align with the strategic directions of organizations and how these projects are managed to increase innovative solutions in organizations (KKAWAK and AMBARI, 2009). In this sense, Turner (2009) deliberates that projects as a vision of a future conjuncture that we would like to achieve. It can be a new computer system, a new production process, a new product, or a new organizational structure, among others.

According to PMI (2019), "the project is a temporary effort to create a unique product, service or result." Due to the complication, the indispensability of cohesively managing the different disciplines present in the projects, such as scope, cost, time, and risk, for example, and constant cultural, technological, political, economic, and social changes, it is increasing essential to achieve active project management. Consequently, each project goes through a series of phases from its conception to its completion. Each phase has its own needs and attributes. As the project goes through these phases, the cumulative amount of outputs and time spent will increase and the remaining time and resources will decrease. This series of phases is known as the life cycle of a project (PMI, 2019).

According to the PMBOK (2017), project management is defined as the use of knowledge, skills, tools, and techniques in project activities to endorse their requirements. Project management is done through the good use and relationship of the processes defined in the PMBOK Guide by PMI that cover:

- Initiation processes;
- Planning processes;
- Execution processes;
- Monitoring and control processes;
- Closure processes.

Each management process has its particularities, outlining the form of good employment, with the use of instruments and techniques. Integration management is about developing, guiding, managing, monitoring, controlling, achieving, and completing. In scope management, the criteria are to schematize, collect conditions, deliberate, create a synthetic structure, authenticate, and control (PINTO; DE BRITO MELLO; SPIEGEL, 2020) the team must be a mixture of different groups with particular resourcefulness inciting the involvement of all parties present. Regardless of the role that each individual occupies in the team, everyone needs to focus on the objectives of the project, and everyone must address a manager to concentrate on the information.

Regarding the benefits of good management Daychoum (2005) highlights the following:

1. prevents surprises during the fulfillment of projects;

2. admits to developing competitive differentials and new techniques, since the whole procedure is being structured;
3. abbreviates risks, to deliberate preventive and corrective actions that can be taken before these risks materialize as problems;
4. adapts efforts to the consumer market and the customer;
5. provides budgets before spending begins;
6. makes decisions both agile by structuring and making information available;
7. improves the management control of all phases of the project, due to the detailing carried out in advance;
8. promotes and guides project reviews that are derived from changes in the market or competitive environment, improving the suitability of the project;
9. better allocates people, equipment, and materials needed; documents and promotes evaluations for future projects.

Gray and Larson (2016) ensure that there is a strong relationship between the processes and benefits of project management adapted to the organizational culture and the success of project management. Still, for the authors, organizations can successfully manage projects within the organizational structure, as long as the organizational culture stimulates the connection of processes in the project environment.

2.2 INDUSTRY 4.0 THE LIGHT OF THEORY

The steam engine - between 1760 and 1840 - distinguished the first revolution of industry; the second was exposed by the use of electricity in industrial processes in the late nineteenth century; the third revolution led in the 1960s with the use of ICT and industrial automation. Industry 4.0 is an initiative of German origin, which aims at the integration of operating systems in manufacturing with information and communication technologies (ICT), forming cyber-physical systems for manufacturing (JESCHKE et al., 2017; QIN; LIU; GROSVENOR, 2016).

Still, some researchers prefer to adopt the term *Industrial Internet of Things* (SMIT et al., 2016), because it is semantically more pertinent to technological development, while Industry 4.0 also mentions the economic impact announced with such development (JESCHKE et al., 2017). In the world context, Germany is one of the most competitive manufacturing industries in the world, largely because of its competence to manage difficult industrial processes, with tasks performed by dissimilar partners, separated from each other. (KAGERMANN; WAHLSTER; HELBIG, 2013).

The government of Germany has released a collection of strategic thoughts that forms among the main data of formalization of the Industry 4.0 enterprise in the world context (KAGERMANN; WAHLSTER; HELBIG, 2013). The indications compressed there summarize the concepts and opinions of the initiative, openly pointing out eight priority areas of action, they are:

1. Inter commercial integration, with the design of an allusion architecture for Industry 4.0;
2. Design of planning models and exploration of industrial processes;
3. Improvement of communication infrastructure;
4. Security (in such a way of people and environments as of sensitive information and data);
5. Organization and corporate governance, aiming to take better advantage of the business knowledge of the professionals involved;
6. Continuous professional development;

7. Regulation, to protect corporate data, provide clear responsibility to the parties involved and curb illegal activities;
8. Efficiency in the use of production resources, minimizing the impact of inconsequential raw material expenses.

As a result of this metamorphosis, Industry 4.0 can currently be considered a new industrial era, with the support of connectivity platforms employed in the sector (REISCHAUER, 2018), and the result of the increasing digitalization and simulation of organizations, especially in manufacturing processes and technologies (CHUI, KARA, CHAN, 2020; FATORACHIAN; KAZEMI, 2018). With the mastery of the appropriate instruments, it is permissible that the life of the professional of this segment changes amazingly, echoing in the flexibility, working time, health, demography, and privacy of the people. This is an attribute with the potential to cushion the distance between the large and the small organization, coining new opportunities for business and commercial relations (KAGERMANN; WAHLSTER; HELBIG, 2013).

In BRAZIL, THE CONCEPT OF "INDUSTRY 4.0" IS BEING SEEN AS THE "4TH INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION" AND HAS BEEN EXHIBITED ESPECIALLY BY GERMAN MULTINATIONAL COMPANIES (DAUDT; WILLCOX, 2016). THE AUTHORS EMPHASIZE THAT EVEN BRINGING POSITIVIST APPEARANCES THE CHARACTERISTICS AND ASPECTS OF ITS PRACTICE WOULD CONSTITUTE THE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY ADJUSTED WITH TECHNOLOGIES ALREADY TRIED AND SUPERIMPOSED, THAT IS, THIS AGITATION COULD BE CONSIDERED MORE AS AN EVOLUTION OF A BROAD METHOD THAT WAS ALREADY IN PROGRESS.

3 METHODOLOGICAL PROCEDURES

The methodological approach of this study is quantitative with an exploratory objective, so the technique used was bibliometric. The quantitative approach was employed due to the nature of the research because this method allows the data to be treated and quantified (RICHARDSON, 1985). The approach is used to describe situations and events to better understand reality (MARTINS and THEÓPHILO, 2016) of Cooper and Schindler (2016), the exploratory study is employed when the researcher does not have a clear idea of the problems that will arise during the study. Knowing that the bibliometric technique is about measuring the development of scientific publications. In other words, this technique helps to perceive at which stage the researched area is (SPINAK, 1996).

Thus, there are three main laws of bibliometrics: Bradford's Law, (journal productivity), Zipf's Law, (frequency of words), and Lotka's Law, (scientific productivity of authors). The authors conceptualize, in their research, the main bibliometric laws and principles, including their study objectives (GUEDES, BORSCHIVER, 2005). For better visualization and understanding of the results of the work, the *VOSviewer software* will be used, which in the view of the author's Van Eck and Waltman (2010) is a program indicated for architecting and conceiving bibliometric maps. The *Excel software* was used to elaborate the spreadsheets and organize the data of this research. In the following sections, the results obtained from the analyses will be provided and discussed, through the support of the aforementioned techniques and tools, as well as the final considerations and possibilities of future research.

4 PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

Initially to start the search in the *Scopus* database, the following words "Project management" were typed in the search field plus the Boolean operator AND "Industry 4.0" the terms all in English. In terms of the research results, the period outlined was from 2010 to April 2020.

Table 1: Basic bibliometric data "Scopus"

<i>Scopus Database</i>	
Search Terms	"Project management" and "Industry 4.0"
Search Fields	"title, abstract e key words"
Total Works Found	63
Authors	167
Sources of Publication	26
Institutions	95
Countries	37
Knowledge Areas	16
Publication Types	2

Source: prepared by the authors (2020).

From the analysis of the documents, it is possible to draw a timeline of the publications.

Figure 1 - Number of articles versus years of publications

Source: prepared by the authors (2020).

From 2010 to 2013 there were no publications already in 2014 had two publications, 2015 had five publications, 2016 there were four publications, 2017 had five in 2018 there was an increase in publications with the themes of this study with eighteen publications, 2019 there was another increase in publications compared to

2018 with twenty-four articles published and ending in 2020 had four publications due to the beginning of the current year.

4.1 PROFILE TWO NEWSPAPERS

From Bradford's Law (1949), it was possible to realize that the 5 journals that most published the terms "Project management" and "Industry 4.0" in the *Scopus* database first were the journal *Procedia Computer Science* this journal is from the Netherlands has an impact factor of 47 according to its area of knowledge in computer science and had four documents in the base, the second was the journal *Iop Conference Series Materials Science And Engineering* presented three papers its area of knowledge is materials engineering it is located in the UK its impact factor H is 24. For a better understanding of the journals that published the most, Figure 2 was elaborated.

Figure 2 - The 5 journals that published the most on the subject of this research

Source: prepared by the authors (2020).

Following the reasoning of the analysis in third place the journal *Advances In Intelligent Systems And Computing* the journal presented 2 documents in the database its country of origin is Germany has an impact factor H of 23 its area of knowledge is control and automation engineering, in fourth place the journal *IFAC Papers online* also presented 2 documents is derived from the area of automation is fixed in Austria and its impact factor H is 52 and finally, the journal *Lecture Notes In Mechanical Engineering* had also 2 documents its country of origin is the United States has an impact factor H of 8 its area of knowledge in mechanical engineering. All the impact factors of the journals were analyzed according to the *Scimago Journal & Country Rank*.

4.2 PUBLICATION BY AUTHORS

From the law Lotka (1926), (scientific productivity of authors), which most published was Dominik T. Matt is affiliated with to Center for Innovation Engineering IEC, the Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, Bozen-Bolzano, Italy has one has 802 citations in the research base and an H of 52, according to the author Pinheiro de Lima, And has dose Scopus base documents on the subject of this research he is affiliated

to Federal Technological University of Paraná, Curitiba, Brazil has 516 citations and an impact factor in the base of 12, in third the author Deschamps, F., is affiliated to the Pontifical Catholic University of Paraná, Curitiba, Brazil, also has 2 documents has 444 citations in the base and an impact factor of 6. To show the number of publications per author, Figure 3 was elaborated.

Figure 3 – The 5 authors who will publish the most in the *Scopus* database

Source: prepared by the authors (2020).

Fourth place the author Emmer, C. is affiliated with PROSTEP AG, Darmstadt, Germany has 2 documents has 44 citations in the database and an impact factor of 4 finalizing the analysis the author Pfouga, A. is affiliated with Ivip TheDarmstadt association, Hessen, Germany, has two documents has 82 citations and an impact factor based on 4. This ranking of authors is based on the number of documents in the first analysis there was an equal number of publications among the authors and another filter was made by the number of citations of each author thus generating the 5 authors who published the most.

4.3 FREQUENCIES OF THE MOST EVIDENT KEYWORDS

When applying Zipf's Law (1949), we found a correlation between the number of words and the frequency of their use, and it is concluded that there is an essential asymmetry in the similar choice and use of words. The most mentioned words were first project management 54 mentions, second in industry 4.0 which was cited 40 times, third place information management was mentioned 16 times, in fourth embedded systems 9 citations and last with 6 citations each the words manufacturing, *big data*, and *software designer*. To show the keywords, we chose to create Figure 4.

Figure 4 – The 5 most cited words

Source: VOSviewer® Software (2020).

The colors of the *clusters* are occasional and fit as a way to illustrate and delimit the various groups of words, having no other definition. However, the place where they appear in the bibliometric graph is not random, because it indicates the surroundings that the surroundings have with each other within the bibliometric *cluster* itself. The size of each *cluster* also has a specific meaning and recommends the number of times such a word appears in the group of articles estimated in the bibliometric study. The relevance of the word is spontaneously appropriate to the diameter of its *cluster*. Given the considerable sample of 63 articles, the present bibliometric study aspired to conform to the main articles,

4.4 COUNTRIES THAT PUBLISHED THE MOST

In this analysis, we sought to see the predominance of publications or the countries that most published on the subject of project management and industry 4.0 in the case Germany for being the cradle of industry 4.0 had the highest number of publications with thirteen documents published in the period from 2010 to 2020, second the United Kingdom with five publications, in third Italy, Spain, and Australia with four publications, in fourth the United States and South Africa. Figure 5 shows the countries that have published the most on the research topic.

Figure 5 – Countries that publish the most about project management and industry 4.0

Source: VOSviewer® Software (2020).

In the case of Brazil, it is in fifth place with two documents in the entire period analyzed.

5 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Employing bibliometric applications to the theme project management and Industry 4.0 verified the relevance of the same for scientific production due to the great growth of publications on the subject in recent years, reaching its peak in 2019 with twenty-four publications. Another indicator of the current popularity on the subject is the number of authors addressing the subject that were 167 authors between 2014 and 2020, the ones who published the most were listed as the *Tops Fives* on project management and industry 4.0 which are Dominik T. Matt, Pinheiro de Lima, Deschamps, F highlighting the two authors are Brazilian (DAUDT; WILLCOX, 2016), Emmer, C, Pfouga, A The last two authors are Germans who was where Industry 4.0 was born (KAGERMANN; WAHLSTER; HELBIG, 2013).

The *Tops Fives* according to Bradford's Law (1949) the journal *Procedia Computer Science* and the journal *Advances In Intelligent Systems And Computing* are directly linked to the area of automation and computing (JESCHKE et al., 2017; QIN; LIU; GROSVENOR, 2016), and its relationship and integration of the research theme with other journals such as the journals *Iop Conference Series Materials Science And Engineering* and *Lecture Notes In Mechanical Engineering* that are directly linked to industry and its ramifications in intelligent manufacturing processes (CHUI, KARA, CHAN, 2020; FATORACHIAN; KAZEMI, 2018). Another suit that comes to be an industry 4.0 paradox that also relates to project management, (PMI, 2019) is the internet of things that have by definitions, for the most part, submerged sensors or microchips that, are connected to physical objects or things (JESCHKE et al., 2017).

In the question of keywords we can see that there was a predominance of the terms of this research, but also emerged other terms such as information management that according to Chui, Kara, and Chan 2020 is due to the consequence of the increasing digitization and simulation in the manufacturing parks, referring to the manufacturing processes in a 3D and 4.0 environment. Embedded systems and the words like manufacturing, *big data*, and *software designer* were also cited (CHUI, KARA, CHAN, 2020).

We can say that Germany is still the country that most cares about research in project management and industry 4.0 due to its number of publications in the *Scopus* database with 13 documents (KAGERMANN; WAHLSTER; HELBIG, 2013), Brazil has 2 documents in the *Scopus* database following the search criteria of this research, we conclude that this is an emerging phenomenon still in the country, but we already have research and researchers with extreme relevance this research theme (DAUDT; WILLCOX, 2016).

5.1 LIMITATIONS OF RESEARCH AND FUTURE STUDIES

Concerning the limitations in the research we can consider the limitation of the method because there are more laws applied to bibliometrics and scientometrics, the question of having used a single source of research in the *Scopus* database. For future research it is recommended to use other databases such as *Spell*, *Science Direct*, *Scielo*, *Emerald*, *Sage*, etc... One could make combinations like project management and industry 4.0 and supply chain management or project management and industry 4.0 and the internet of things.

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